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The Effect of Children's Literature Works on Students' Tendency to Violence

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Abstract

In this study, it was tried to determine whether the works of children's literature containing violence are effective on the violent tendencies of 7th grade students. In the research, one of the mixed method designs, triangulation (diversification) design was used. In the quantitative dimension of the study, the pre-test and post-test control group model was used, among the quasi-experimental designs, and in the qualitative dimension, the phenomenology design was used. The study group of the study consists of 50 students, 25 of whom are control and 25 of them are experimental groups, studying in 7th grade in Kahraman Kids Secondary School in Edremit district of Van province. In the study, the aggression scale developed by Buss and Perry as a quantitative data tool and adapted to Turkish by Demirtaş Madran; Semi-structured interview form was used as the qualitative data tool. SPSS 18 statistical package program was used in the analysis of quantitative data, and content analysis method was used in the analysis of qualitative data. According to the quantitative results of the study, no significant difference was found between the scores of the experimental and control groups in the post-test of the aggression scale at the end of the application. According to the data obtained through the semi-structured interview form, it was determined that the students mostly liked the children's books containing violence, they found them exciting, fluent and beautiful.

Keywords: Violence, Tendency to Violence, Children's Literature, Violence in Books

1. Introduction

1.1 Children's Literature and Children's Reading Tendencies By Ages

Stating that the concept of children's literature emerged in the first quarter of the 20th century, Karatay (2007) states that all of the products that can appeal to the understanding, emotion, imagination and thought world of children in the developing age can be called children's literature. According to him, children's literature is all oral, written and visual products that can appeal to the world of thought of young individuals of the society who are not adults and need to be educated.

Much has been said about the content and quality of children's literature. According to Şirin (1994), literature for children is above all language. Literature enriches the child's world. Good literature develops literary taste and a sense of beauty. It contributes to the child's knowledge of himself / herself and his / her environment, to speak well and to develop his / her tastes; prepares the ground for the emergence of talents; Improves thinking and commenting skills. Again, according to him, the most effective genre that feeds the child's soul is literature.

Children's literature works that contribute to the affective, cognitive and spiritual development of the child reader must be qualified and appropriate for the child's development and age group. Because children's interest in reading and books varies at certain ages. It is stated that children are between the ages of 6-7 interested in short, illustrated fairy tales with animals, giants and fairies; at 9-10 ages, tales of children tools and inventions, and works on the lives of famous men; 12-15 years old children, respectively, more interested in works and tales about home life, fairy tales about school life, fairy tales, love stories and works dealing with historical subjects (Kantarcıoğlu, 1991).

In the classifications made according to age groups, it is called the adventure period between 12-15 years. The child is in the pre-adolescent development stage during this period. At this age, there is an increasing interest in group formation and demonstrations of toughness. Reading interest is also in this direction. In this period, emotionalism and self-prominence are seen, so there is a tendency towards adventure books, emotional romance novels and travel books (Güneş, 2017).

On the other hand, children in the 11-14 age group also enjoy subjects related to adventure, hobbies, family life, interests and likes (Çakır, 2013).

According to a study conducted on middle school students, it was seen that 50.5% of the participants preferred texts like adventure, 48.2% fear, and 47.3% comedy (Bayat & Çetinkaya, 2018).

1.2 Reflection of Violence on Children's Literature

Violence is one of the most important problem areas of the age (Yılmaz & Destegüloğlu, 2019). According to Şirin, the world we live in is a world that produces violence and where violence is globalized. Children are the weakest and unprotected object of the culture of violence, and children grow up recognizing all types of violence (Şirin, 2016, p.204).

One of the media elements that can lead children to violence is children's books (Yavuzer, 2009, p. 243). There are two different opinions about whether or not there should be violent elements in children's books. While the first of these claims that violence should not be included in children's books in any way, the second opinion argues that violence can be included in the books provided that it is not presented as a solution (Yılmaz & Destegüloğlu, 2019).

According to Şirin, even if concrete violence in real life is reflected in literature in isolation, not every child can distinguish it. Literature can have a reinforcing effect on a child who has embraced violence. The book can fulfill a potential stimulating or stimulating function. (Şirin, 2016, p.205).

Sever (2002) draws attention to the existence of an understanding that contradicts the aims of the Basic Law of National Education and the universal provisions of the Convention on the Rights of the Child in some books prepared for children and young people starting from pre-school period to the youth period in our country.

He states that so-called children's books can meet with children in libraries, bookstores and textbooks. According to him, the emotional and mental health of our children is damaged by violent and ideological books.

Children are surrounded by guided, against human nature, intended to destroy human sensitivity, and naturalize aggression and violence. In addition, Sever is opposed to children's books that affirm violence and show it as a

way to solve problems, instead of displaying an understanding that is totally opposed to violence in children's books; argues that these books are not suitable for children.

According to Neydim (2003), in order for children to cope with their own fears, they need to encounter texts with reflected elements of violence and fear. Although it contains elements of violence and fear, Harry Potter was fondly read by children, and according to children, this book helped them cope with their fears. Neydim, as a result of his studies with students at various levels, objects to the display of children's literature as the source of the phenomenon of violence in children. According to him, these children did not even encounter proper literary texts, let alone encounter violence in children's literature. Therefore, there have never been literary texts that internalize violence in children. The real problem is in the understanding of education. The literary text should not be placed before the child as an absolute authority, and the child's right to criticize, object and refuse should not be taken away.

Nimon (1993) states that violence should be included in children's books. According to him, even if it is annoying, children should read these books in order to confront the realities of life, and these books take on the task of preparing children for the phenomenon of violence in real life. In addition, Nimon considers the exposure of the pain caused by violence in children's books containing violence important for the child to realize the reality of violence.

In the literature review, many studies have been found that deal with the phenomenon of violence in the context of children's literature. These studies examined both domestic and foreign works on the basis of the phenomenon of violence and the principle of relativity to children (Aktaş & Uzuner Yurt, 2017; Fırat, Güleç & Şahin, 2013; Güney 2007; Kuzu, 2003; Fırtına, 2003; İçözü, 2003; İlkan and Koç, 2003; Running, 2003; Sivri, 2003). There is only one applied study examining the children's readers' thoughts and reactions about the violent books. In this study carried out by Kayman (2020), seven stories of Ömer Seyfettin, which include different types of violence and different characters, were read to 5th grade students, and their reactions to these works were tried to be determined. In the study, it was observed that the students did not like these mostly violent works and wanted to exclude the scenes of violence from the work.

After reviewing the relevant literature, no other study other than the above-mentioned applied study was found. On the other hand, it was necessary to conduct such a study as it was aimed to determine how the violence in the works of other authors in Turkish and World Literature is perceived by students in older age groups and whether these works affect their violent tendencies. It is thought that the study will contribute to the literature and add breadth.

1.3 Aim of the research

The aim of this study is to determine whether children's books with violent content are effective on the violent tendencies of middle school 7th grade students. For this purpose, answers to the following questions were sought:

1. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores that the experimental and control group students got from the aggression scale?
2. What are the opinions of the experimental group students about the violent books they read?

2. Research Model

In this study, one of the mixed method designs, triangulation (diversification) design was used. The diversification pattern includes the collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data separately. The purpose of this design is to combine the results obtained from the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data (Creswell, 2017b: 37). In the research process, after the quantitative and qualitative data were collected, they were analyzed and combined.

In the quantitative dimension of the study, a model with pre-test and post-test control group, which is one of the quasi-experimental designs, was used. In the experimental study, measurements are made at the pre-test and post-test stages with measurement tools (Creswell, 2017a; 170).

In the qualitative dimension of the study, the phenomenology design was used. Phenomenology is a research model used to investigate the phenomena that people are aware of in daily life but do not have in-depth knowledge (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). This study was also aimed at this study, and it was tried to examine students' views on violent children's books in detail using qualitative data collection tools.

2.1 The Study Group

Research was carried out with 7th grade students studying secondary school in the city of Van in Turkey. In the study, which included an experiment (N=25) and a control group (N=25), two classes with similar Turkish course achievements were selected. The two selected classes were divided into experimental and control groups by lot. The descriptive data of the experimental and control group students are presented comparatively in the tables below.

Table 1: Gender distribution of the experimental and control group students

Groups	Female	%	Male	%	Total
Experiment	13	52,0	12	48,0	25
Control	14	56,0	11	44,0	25

According to Table 1, there are 13 girls, 12 boys in the experimental group, 14 girls and 11 boys in the control group, 25 students in each group, and 50 students in total.

Table 2: Education levels of the mothers of the experimental and control group students

Education Levels	Experiment	%	Control	%	Total
Illiterate	7	28,0	8	32,0	15
Primary school graduate	10	40,0	9	36,0	19
Secondary school graduate	8	32,0	8	32,0	16
Total	25	100	25	100	50

Looking at Table 2, the mothers of the students in both groups are "illiterate," primary school graduates and secondary school graduates, at three different education levels. In addition, it is seen that the education levels of the mothers of the students in the experimental and control groups are close to each other.

Table 3: Educational levels of the fathers of the experimental and control group students

Education Levels	Experiment	%	Control	%	Total
Illiterate	4	16,0	5	20,0	9
Primary school graduate	8	32,0	9	36,0	17
Secondary school graduate	7	28,0	6	24,0	13
High school graduate	6	24,0	5	20,0	11
Total	25	100	25	100	50

According to Table 3, the fathers of the students in both groups have four different educational levels: "illiterate," primary school graduate, secondary school graduate, and high school graduate. In addition, it is seen that the education levels of the fathers of the students in the experimental and control groups are close to each other.

Table 4: Average family income levels of the experimental and control group students

Income Level	Experiment	%	Control	%	Total
Between 0-1500 TL	15	60,0	17	68,0	32
Between 1500-3000 TL	7	28,0	6	24,0	13
Between 3000-4500 TL	3	12,0	2	8,0	5
Total	25	100	25	100	50

When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that the average family income level of the students in both groups varies between 0 and 4500 TL, and the average family income levels of the students in both groups are close to each other.

2.2 Application Process

The research was carried out after the approval of the research permit obtained from the Governorship through the Van Provincial Directorate of National Education. In the study, attention was paid to the fact that the experimental and control group students were close to each other in terms of Turkish course success and demographic characteristics. The application part of the research lasted 8 weeks. Help was received from the school counselor during the implementation process and it was provided to support the students throughout the application. After the pre-test was applied to the students in the experimental and control groups, four books were read to both the experimental and control groups. It was paid attention that the books read by the control group were non-violent. These books are as follows:

1. Sevim Ak's work titled "Uçurtmam Bulut Şimdi" (My Kite is A Cloud Now)
2. Yalvaç Ural's work titled "Korkuluğun Kalbi" (The Heart of the Scarecrow)
3. Mustafa Ruhi Sirin's work "Her Çocuğun Bir Yıldızı Var" (Every Child Has a Star)
4. Gülten Dayıoğlu's work titled "Dünya Çocukların Olsa" (I Wish The World Belonged to Children)

The students in the experimental group, on the other hand, read four violent books. These books are as follows:

1. Ahmet Rasim's work called "Falaka" (Bastinado)
2. Kemalettin Tuğcu's work called "Kuklacı" (The Puppeteer)
3. Muallim Naci's work titled "Ömer'in Çocukluğu" (Ömer's Childhood)
4. Mark Twain's work titled "Tom Sawyer"

After the students in the experimental and control groups read the aforementioned books, the researchers applied a post-test to both groups. Subsequently, the students in the experimental group were given an interview form, and they were asked to express their opinions in writing in order to determine their thoughts about the books they read and the scenes of violence in these books. In all the studies carried out throughout the application, care was taken to avoid directing expressions, attitudes and behaviors that could affect the students' thoughts.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

In the study, "Aggression Scale" was used as a quantitative data tool and "Semi-Structured Interview Form" was used as a qualitative data tool.

2.4 Aggression Scale

Aggression Scale is a scale developed by Buss and Perry (1992) and adapted into Turkish by Demirtaş Madran (2012). This scale, which has 29 items and 4 factors, is prepared in 5-point Likert type. In the reliability studies of the scale, the internal consistency coefficient was calculated and test-retest and test halving methods were used. The internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) coefficient was 0,85 for the whole scale, 0,78 for the physical aggression sub-factor, 0,71 for the hostility sub-factor, 0,71 for the anger sub-factor, and 0,48 for the verbal aggression sub-factor. In order to determine the criterion validity, the correlation of the Multidimensional Anger Scale (Balkaya & Şahin, 2003) of the Turkish form with the "anger-related behaviors" subscale was examined,

and it was determined that the correlation between the two scales was significant at the level of 0,01 (Demirtaş-Madran, 2012).

2.5 Semi-Structured Interview Form

After the application, a semi-structured interview form was prepared by the researchers to determine the students' views on violent children's books. In order to determine whether the questions in the interview form were suitable for the purpose or not, the opinions of a total of six people, including three Turkish teachers, two faculty members, and a psychological counselor, were consulted. After taking expert opinions, the questions in the form were finalized and used in the study.

2.6 Data Analysis

In order to determine which statistical tests should be used before analyzing the scores obtained by the students from the data collection tools, it was checked whether the total scores obtained in the pre-test and post-test were normally distributed (normality test). According to the results of the normality tests, the test types used in the analysis were determined.

The skewness and kurtosis values indicating the normality value of the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental and control groups regarding the aggression scale are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Results of normality tests for the aggression scale of the experimental and control groups

Groups	Test Type	Skewness	Kurtosis
Experimental Group	Pretest	,718	,294
	Posttest	,901	,067
Control Group	Pretest	,996	,297
	Posttest	,961	-,006

According to George and Mallery (2003), the skewness and kurtosis values of a scale between -2 and +2 indicate that it is in a normal distribution. In the research, when the reference mentioned above is taken into consideration, it is seen that the skewness and kurtosis values of the experimental and control groups show a normal distribution.

In this study, in which the effect of violent children's literature works on students' tendencies to violence was examined, "SPSS 18" statistical package program was used to understand whether there was a significant difference between the experimental group and the control group students in terms of pre-test and post-test. Independent groups t test was used to determine the difference between experimental and control groups. Significance level was accepted as at least 0.05.

The qualitative data of the research were analyzed through content analysis. The process in content analysis is to gather similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and to interpret them in a way that the reader can understand (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). In this analysis process, firstly, the opinions of the students were listed, the codes were extracted and the code numbers were calculated. Later, the codes and student responses related to the codes were given in tables and interpreted. For the reliability of the content analysis, the answers given to the questions were coded by two coders. The reliability coefficient between the coders was calculated as 0,92 by the formula of Miles and Huberman (1994). Reliability = Consensus / (Consensus + Disagreement). Based on this formula, the result was $23 / (23 + 2) = 0,92$.

3. Results

Findings of the statistical analysis of the data obtained from the research are given below.

3.1 Findings for the first question of the research

The results of the independent measurements t-test indicating the difference between the pre-test averages of the scores obtained by the students in the experimental and control groups from the aggression scale are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Results regarding the pre-test scores that the experimental group and control group students got from the aggression scale

Grups	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	p
Experiment	25	65,76	9,33	48	,156	,877
Control	25	65,28	12,23			

As a result of the analysis, no statistically significant difference was found between the experimental group students 'pretest mean score ($\bar{X} = 65.76$) and the control group students' average score ($\bar{X} = 65,28$) [$t(48) = ,156$ ($p = ,877$)]. According to the pre-test results, it can be said that the aggression tendencies of the experimental and control groups are close to each other before the application. The results of the independent measurements t-test indicating the difference between the post-test averages taken by the students in the experimental and control groups from the aggression scale are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Results regarding the post-test scores that the experimental group and control group students got from the aggression scale

Grups	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t	p
Experiment	25	64,16	7,987	48	,282	,779
Control	25	63,44	9,937			

As a result of the analysis, no statistically significant difference was found between the experimental group students 'post-test score average ($\bar{X} = 64,16$) they got from the aggression scale and the control group students' mean score ($\bar{X} = 63,44$) from the aggression scale [$t(48) = ,282$ ($p = ,779$)] This shows that the experimental group students' tendency to violence does not increase after reading violent books.

3.2 Findings for the second question of the research

This section includes content analysis of the opinions taken from the experimental group students in order to evaluate the books they read. In the study, 5 open-ended questions were asked to the students, and themes and codes were obtained from the answers given by the students. The results obtained in this way are presented in a table and examples of the answers given by the students to the questions are given. In order to get students' opinions about which works they prefer more, first of all, the following questions has been asked: "Which features do you look for in the books you read, what kind of books do you like more?". In this direction, the answers given by the students to the questions are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Students' opinions about the features of the books they like

Student Views	f	%
It should include action and mystery	8	32,0
It should be interesting	7	28,0
Its content should be good	4	16,0
The way of expression should be good	2	8,0
Should be clear	2	8,0
Must be emotional	2	8,0
Total	25	100

As seen in Table 8, based on the answers given by the students to the above question, six categories were created. These can be listed as “should include action and mystery (32,0%)”, interesting (28,0%), good content (16,0%), good expression (8,0%), understandable (8,0%), must be emotional (8,0%)”. According to the data obtained, it is seen that students like interesting books with more action and mystery. Some of the students stated that they liked the books with good content and expression and in which emotional subjects were told. In this context, some students' views are as follows:

Of the books I have read, I like to read the most action and mystery books. Because these are among the books that touch me the most. (Ö5).

I am impressed that the books I read are interesting. (Ö12).

If there is a good content in a book it is worth to read. Because I like books about love, friendship and friendships more. (T8).

I look at the way of expression. I always read the ones with good narration. (Ö9).

I like clear ones. I get tired of the books I don't understand (T4)

I am an emotional person. I would be impressed if I read emotional books. (S13)

During the implementation process, four violent books were read to the experimental group students. In order to get the opinions of the students about the first book they read called Falaka, the following question has been asked: “What are your thoughts about the book called Falaka? Can you explain?”. In this direction, the answers given by the students to the questions are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Students' views about the book called Falaka

Student Views	f	%
Beautiful	10	40,00
Exciting	7	28,00
Full of violence	4	16,00
Distressing	3	12,00
Depressing	1	4,00
Total	25	100

As seen in Table 9, based on the answers given by the students to the above question, five categories were created. These can be listed as beautiful (40,00%), exciting (28,00%), violent (16,00%), saddening (12,00%), depressing (4,00%). The data obtained show that most of the students liked the book called Falaka and thought it was beautiful and exciting. Some students stated that the book was violent, distressing and depressing. In this context, some students' views are as follows:

It was a nice book, I read it right away. I can recommend it to others. The thing that draws my attention about the book is that the child is afraid of the teacher, in fact, there was no need for this fear (T2).

Falaka is a very exciting and mysterious book. That's why I liked the book Falaka. I read it fondly because I had read it before (T5).

I liked the book. He was generally excited. Actually, it could have been a little more thrilling. I think there should be constant action. It is more enjoyable (T6).

There is a lot of violence in the book. Hodja always punish students by bastinado. This is not good at all. I don't think it's fun (T15).

I was very upset while reading the book. Students are always beaten. I think it should not be like this, bastinado is not good (S6).

I didn't like the book. To tell you the truth, I was very depressed. Students were beaten (T13).

It is seen that the majority of the students used positive expressions about the book called Falaka. Students describe the violent incidents in the book as excited and mysterious. In addition, it is observed that the students are not affected by the violent scenes in the book.

In order to get the opinions of the students about the another book called "Ömer's Childhood?", they have been asked "What are your thoughts on the book "Ömer's Childhood?" Can you explain?" In this direction, the answers given by the students to the questions are shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Students' opinions about the book named Ömer's Childhood

Student Views	f	%
Fluent	7	28,0
Beautiful	7	28,0
Full of adventure	4	16,0
Depressing	4	16,0
Boring	3	12,0
Total	25	100

As seen in Table 10, based on the answers given by the students to the above question, five categories were created. These can be listed as fluent (28,00%), beautiful (28,00%), full of adventure (16,00%), distressing (16,00%), boring (12,00%). The data obtained show that the majority of the students liked the book named Ömer's Childhood and stated that the book was beautiful and full of adventure. Some students stated that they did not like the book and that they were sad and bored while reading. In this context, some students' views are as follows:

Ömer's Childhood book was good, I liked the book and its fiction was good (T6).

The book was good. I finished in a day. I found the part where the dog attacked Ömer excited (T4).

I think Ömer's Childhood was an adventurous book. I love such adventurous ones (T11).

The book was not good. I was upset while reading the book. I was saddened by what happened to Omer (T5).

The book was boring. I think it could have been a little more exciting (T9).

Students mostly gave positive opinions about the book named Ömer's Childhood; They stated that they liked the book, were impressed by it, and found it fluid and full of adventure. Considering these views, it is seen that the students are not affected by the violent events much, but they find these events exciting, fluent and adventurous.

In order to get the opinions of the students about Tom Sawyer, another book that they read, firstly, the question of "What are your thoughts on the book Tom Sawyer? Can you explain?" has been asked. In this direction, the answers given by the students to the questions are shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Students' views about the book named Tom Sawyer

Student Views	f	%
Full of adventure	8	32,00
Exciting	6	24,00
Fluent	5	20,00
Boring	3	12,00
Containing violence	3	12,00
Total	25	100

As seen in Table 11, based on the answers given by the students to the above question, five categories were created. These can be listed as adventurous (32,00%), exciting (24,00%), fluid (20,00%), boring (12,00%), violent (12,00%). According to the data obtained, most of the students stated that they liked the book named Tom Sawyer and found it full of adventure, exciting and fluent. Some students, on the other hand, stated that they did not like the book, that they were bored while reading, and that there were violent scenes in it. In this context, the views of some students in the study group are cited below:

I liked the book. An adventurous book. Tom's days are always eventful. I like such books very much (T3).

I think the exciting parts were very good. It was an exciting book. I think there should always be action in the books (T4).

Tom Sawyer was both beautiful and fluent. I especially liked Tom's mischief. The writer thought well (T15).

Tom Sawyer drew my attention and I read it with enthusiasm. Because the adventure was too much. Something caught my attention in the book. At the end of the book, if the Native American Joe had not been stuck in the cave and had not died, it would have been better if Tom and his friend set up a trap and catch him instead (T7). The book was boring to me. There was no incident in it. I think I expected it to be a little more exciting and I didn't like the story as it is (T9).

I do not like. There is always evil. They kill each other. There is violence. I think there should be more good people. Tom must be a nice guy. It should help people (T6).

Students mostly gave positive opinions about Tom Sawyer. The students stated that the book was full of adventure, exciting and fluent. Some students stated that they found the book boring and did not like the scenes of violence. In this context, it was observed that most of the students were not affected by the violent incidents in the work.

Another book that the students read was Kemalettin Tuğcu's work called Kuklacı. In order to get the opinions of the students in the study group about the work named "Puppeteer," what are your thoughts about the piece named "Puppeteer? Can you explain?" The question has been asked. In this direction, the answers given by the students to the questions are shown in the table below.

Table 12: Students' views about the book called Kuklacı

Student Views	f	%
Exciting	7	28,00
Fluent	6	24,00
Beautiful	4	16,00
Distressing	4	16,00
Depressing	2	8,00
Violent	2	8,00
Total	25	100

As seen in Table 12, based on the answers given by the students to the above question, six categories were created. These can be listed as exciting (28,00%), fluid (24,00%), beautiful (16,00%), saddening (16,00%), depressing (8,00%), violent (8,00%)) are listed as. The data obtained show that most of the students liked the book called Puppeteer and thought the book was beautiful, exciting and fluent. Some students stated that the book was distressing, depressing and containing violence. Some students' views about the book are given below: *The Puppeteer was a very exciting book. I liked this book. The events were very exciting, I think the fiction is good (T25).*

I liked the book. It's a fluent book. I like such books. I never wanted to leave the book (T18).

I think it was a good book. It wasn't boring. I read it to the end because it is well written (T3).

I didn't like the book very much. People in the family say very bad words. They don't like each other. I got sad while reading the book (T6).

I never liked the book. I was very depressed while reading the events between them. They work behind each other. They are yelling and calling (T9).

I don't think the book is beautiful. The man hits the woman and blood flows from his lips. I do not like such books (T23).

It is seen that the majority of the students used positive expressions about the book called The Puppeteer. The students stated that they liked the events in the book and found them excited. In addition, it was observed that a great majority of the students did not mention the parts in the book containing physical and psychological violence.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

This study, in which it was tried to determine whether children's books with violence content were effective on the violent tendencies of 7th grade students, had both quantitative and qualitative results.

According to the quantitative results of the study, no significant difference was found between the scores of the experimental and control groups in the post-test of the aggression scale at the end of the application. This result revealed that violent children's books are not effective on 7th grade students' violent tendencies.

After the students in the experimental group read the violent books, their opinions were taken through the interview forms and various qualitative results were obtained. In this context, it was determined that the students mostly liked the children's books containing violence, they found them exciting, fluent and beautiful. It was concluded that some students did not like the books, found them distressing, depressing and boring. The aforementioned results led to the opinion that the violence did not affect students in this age group very much.

It is thought that the fact that 7th grade students in the study group liked and find the violent books they read as exciting is related to their developmental period and age group. Because, as Güneş (2007) stated, children in this age group are interested in shows of toughness and tend to adventure books. Çakır (2013) also used similar expressions and stated that students in this age group especially liked books about adventure.

Bayat and Çetinkaya (2018) determined in their study with middle school students that most of the students preferred books containing adventure, fear, and murder. The findings obtained from the aforementioned studies coincide with the results of this research.

On the other hand, in the study conducted by Kayman (2020) with middle school 5th grade students, students stated that they did not like violent works and they did not want to read these works. It is thought that this is due to their age group. Although the results obtained by Kayman in his study do not coincide with the results of this study, the fact that 5th grade students are easily affected by their age (Yavuzer, 1987) and very quickly affected by violent books may have prompted them to react.

Another reason for these students not to be affected by the violent works may be that they think that the events and scenes of violence in the works they read are fictional due to their age. Because, in some of the student views quoted above, it is stated by the students that the scenes of violence in these books are fictions.

Based on the findings obtained from this study, it is possible to conclude that if children's books are read to children of the appropriate age group, the violence contained in these books does not drive them to aggression and does not lead to violence.

As a result, attention should be paid to how violence is included in the books, as Sever's (2002) stated. In these books, it is of great importance for the child reader to make a healthy reading that the violence should not be affirmed and the hero should not reach his goal by using violence. However, considering the age groups, the gradual exposure of children to violent works will help them gain experience and prepare for some negative situations they may encounter in daily life.

References

- Aktaş, E. & Uzuner Yurt, S. (2017). The factors being not "proper for child" in the stories of Ömer Seyfettin in terms of children' literature. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 9(1), 207-223.
- Bayat, N. & Çetinkaya, G. (2018). Reading habits and preferences of secondary school students. *İlköğretim Online*, 17(2), 984-1001.
- Creswell, J. W. (2017a). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. (S. B. Demir, Trans.) Ankara: Eğiten Kitap.

- Creswell, J. W. (2017b). *A Concise Introduction to Mixed Methods Research*. (M. Sözbilir, Trans.) Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Çakır, P. (2013). The research of stories in turkish coursebook in terms of the suitability to the child principle. *Turkish Studies*, 8(1), 1171-1180.
- Demirtaş Madran, H. A. (2012). Reliability and validity of the buss-perry aggression questionnaire-Turkish version. *Turkish Journal of Psychiatry* (23), 1-6.
- Fırat, H., Güleç, H. & Şahin, Ç. (2013). Research on the books prepared for pre-school children from the points of fear and violence elements. *International Journal of Social Science*, 6(5), 217-241.
- Fırtına, Ö. (2003). An example of the element of violence in German children's literature. In *Symposium on violence reflected in children's literature and pediatrics* (pp. 27-31). Eskişehir: Osmangazi University.
- George D. & Mallery P. (2003). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference. 11.0 update* (4th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Güneş, F. (2017). Reading interest and power. *Journal of Education, Theory and Practical Research*, 3(3), 119-128.
- Güney, N. (2007). *The analysis of death and violence in Kemalettin Tuğcu's fifty novel* (Unpublished master's thesis). Atatürk University, Erzurum, Turkey.
- İçöz, N. (2003). Who is afraid of the clown or where the devil is in this? In *Symposium on violence reflected in children's literature and pediatrics* (pp. 58-63). Eskişehir: Osmangazi University.
- İlhan, İ. & Koç, Y. (2003). On the sociological and psychological act of violence reflected on the child in literature. In *Symposium on violence reflected in children's literature and pediatrics* (pp. 10-16). Eskişehir: Osmangazi University.
- Kantarcıoğlu, S. (1991). *The place of fairy tales in education*. İstanbul: MEB Yayınları.
- Karatay, H. (2007). The importance and function of fairy tales in language acquisition and value teaching process. *The Journal of Turkish Educational Sciences*, 5(3), 463-477.
- Kayman, F. (2020). *Research on the perception of violence by 5th grade students who faced violence in fictional texts in the context of Ömer Seyfettin stories* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Atatürk University, Erzurum, Turkey.
- Koşmak, F. (2003). Violence against the child appearing in Jose Mauro de Vasconcelos' My Sweet Orange Tree. In *Symposium on violence reflected in children's literature and pediatrics* (pp. 125-130). Eskişehir: Osmangazi University.
- Kuzu, T. (2003). Stepmother violence in fairy tales. In *Symposium on violence reflected in children's literature and pediatrics* (pp. 22-26). Eskişehir: Osmangazi University.
- Miles, M. B. & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*, California: Sage Publications.
- Neydim, N. (2003). *Children's literature*. İstanbul: Bu Yayınevi.
- Nimon, M. (1993). Violence in children's literature today [microform] / Maureen Nimon Distributed by ERIC Clearinghouse, [Washington, D.C.] <http://www.eric.ed.gov/contentdelivery/servlet/ERICServlet?accno=ED399935>
- Sever, S. (2002). Violence reflected in children's books (an evaluation in the context of the National Education Basic Law and the Convention on the Rights of the Child. *Ankara University Journal of Faculty of Educational Sciences*, 35(1-2), 25-37.
- Sivri, M. (2003). The source of ill-defined children's drama and violence in Kafka's "Letter to His Father" and Susanna Tamaro's "Such a Childhood (For One Voice)." In *Symposium on violence reflected in children's literature and pediatrics* (pp. 81-98). Eskişehir: Osmangazi University.
- Şirin, M. R. (1994). *Children's literature in 99 questions*. İstanbul: Çocuk Vakfı Yayınları.
- Şirin, M. R. (2016). *Children, childhood and children's literature* (1st Ed.). İstanbul: Kapı Yayınları.
- Yavuzer, H. (1987). *Child psychology* (3rd Ed.). İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi.
- Yavuzer, H. (2009). *Child and crime*. İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi.
- Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2016). *Qualitative research methods in social sciences* (10th Edition). Ankara: Seçkin Yayınları.
- Yılmaz, O. & Destegüloğlu, B. (2019). Violence reflected in children's books. *İlköğretim Online*, 18(3), 1099-1112.